

TABLE 1—C.E.C. OF ROOTS (m eq/100 g) AND NUTRIENT CONTENT OF PLANT AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

Growth stage	Root C E C.		P ppm		Fe ppm		Mn ppm	
	BG-39/2	BG-231	BG-39/2	BG-231	BG-29/2	BG-231	BG-29/2	BG-231
Stage-I	21.49	21.00	4333.3	3958.3	910.4	900.1	114.6	100.3
Stage-II	19.66	18.75	4083.3	3666.7	687.5	687.5	80.3	75.0
Stage-III	17.42	16.83	3858.3	3458.0	583.3	572.9	62.3	54.2

the method of determination same. dried roots also show the same C.E.C. as the fresh ones. The plant samples were analysed for P, Fe and Mn by the reported method^{10,11}.

Results and Discussion

The effect of age of plant and nutrient content on C.E.C. of roots are shown in Table 1.

Perusal of Table 1 reveals that varieties of the crop were different in relation to their C.E.C. of roots and in both the cases the root C.E.C. is decreased due to increase in age. Also, the contents of P, Fe and Mn decrease with increase in age, i.e. with decrease in root C.E.C.

The correlation of C.E.C. of roots with age and nutrient content of plants are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RELATIONSHIPS (r) OF ROOT C.E.C. WITH AGE AND NUTRIENT CONTENT OF PLANTS

	Gram varieties	
	BG-39/2	BG-231
C.E.C. vs age	-0.99 ^a	-0.96 ^a
C.E.C. vs P content	0.75 ^b	0.99 ^a
C.E.C. vs Fe content	0.92 ^b	0.93 ^a
C.E.C. vs Mn content	0.97 ^a	0.86 ^b

^aSignificant at 0.1% level.
^bSignificant at 1% level.

^aSignificant at 5% level.

From data presented in Table 2 a highly significant negative correlation was observed between the C.E.C. of roots and age of the plant. The present study also supports the previous works^{1,2,4,5} on other crops. The decrease in root C.E.C. due to increase in age of plant is due to the variation of composition of cells. It is further revealed that a highly significant positive correlation exists between the C.E.C. of roots and content of phosphorus, iron and manganese. Nutrient content and root C.E.C. of both the varieties are decreased due to increase in age. Similar observations were made on other crops^{3,6}. The increase in nutrient content increases the root C.E.C. by increasing cell division and decreasing the non-pectic carbohydrates in the cell wall of the roots.

References

1. A. K. HELMY and M. M. ELGABALY, *Plant Soil*, 1958, 10, 33.
2. L. C. RAM, *Plant Soil*, 1980, 55, 215.
3. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *Plant Soil*, 1978, 49, 661.
4. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1976, 24, 427.
5. S. SINGH and L. C. RAM, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1973, 21, 367.

6. L. SINGH and S. SINGH, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1981, 29, 228.
7. S. G. HEINTZE, *Plant Soil*, 1961, 13, 365.
8. W. M. CROOKE, *Plant Soil*, 1964, 21, 43.
9. R. L. SMITH and A. WALLACE, *Soil Sci.*, 1956, 81, 97.
10. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall India Ltd., New Delhi, 1967.
11. C. S. PIPER, "Soil and Plant Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1942.

Magnetic Susceptibility—A Curious Difference in Behaviour Between an Oil and Its Cake

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THE magnetic characteristics of natural products, like oils, nuts, grains etc. have not been reported so far. The main difficulty in using the magnetic data for such materials is their complex composition, unlike simple organic or inorganic materials. Many of the natural products contain water and complex organic molecules which might mask the true magnetic property of the specimen. It might also be expected that the actual magnetic moments of a material, say, an oil would vary from source to source. However, preliminary measurements of magnetic susceptibility with oils indicate a constant value for each oil obtained from different sources. This observation confirmed that magnetic moments could precisely be quoted for these natural products also. In this note we report the data obtained on some vegetable and animal oils, their cakes and seeds.

Experimental

Commercial samples of oils and seeds were used as such. Each material was obtained from five different sources and the quality of each oil was checked by measuring its density and refractive index. These values agreed, within experimental error, with those reported in the literature. Table I gives the data available on the chemical composition of oil seeds, oilcakes and oils¹⁻⁴.

The magnetic susceptibility for each sample was measured by the Gouy method⁵. The Gouy balance had a provision for weighing correctly to ± 0.05 mg. The magnetic field strength was measured with

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF OIL SEEDS, OIL CAKES AND OILS¹⁻⁴

	Sesame	Groundnut	Coconut
Mineral and trace elements of oil seeds (mg/100 g)			
Ash*	6.6 ± 0.02	3.3 ± 0.09	2.1 ± 0.09
P	872 ± 35	500 ± 8	193 ± 10
Ca	1232 ± 28	77 ± 6	24 ± 4
Mg	521 ± 42	239 ± 4	164 ± 6
Fe	9.3 ± 0.43	2.5 ± 0.23	7.8 ± 0.91
Zn	122 ± 21	39 ± 1.6	50 ± 1.8
Mn	13.2 ± 0.26	11.0 ± 0.76	62.4 ± 3.28
Cu	22.9 ± 1.7	9.0 ± 0.53	10.0 ± 0.91
Cr	0.87 ± 0.052	0.48 ± 0.031	—

Chemical composition of oil cakes (wt %)

	Sesame	Groundnut	Coconut
Moisture	8.19	10.68	12.82
Oil	8.60	5.81	7.50
Albuminoids	38.70	45.12	19.37
Carbohydrates	25.22	30.49	42.33
Fibre	5.17	3.84	12.10
Mineral matter	14.12	4.06	6.48

Fatty acid composition of oils (wt %)

	Sesame	Groundnut	Coconut
Caproic	—	—	02-08
Caprylic	—	—	5-9
Capric	—	—	5-10
Lauric	—	—	44-51
Palmitic	7-10	6-12	7-11
Stearic	3.5-6.0	2-4	1-3
Arachidic	0.4-1.2	5-7	0.2-1.5
Palmitoleic	—	—	Trace
Oleic	35-50	42-72	5-8
Linoleic	37-49	13-28	Trace
Behemic	—	3	—
Lignoceric	—	4	—

*wt %

TABLE 2—VOLUME SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF OILS

Oil	-10 ⁻⁶ (Volume susceptibility at 10 kG)	
	Gouy method	Quincke method
Coconut	0.479	0.469
Refined	0.459	0.450
Gingelly	0.499	0.503
Groundnut	0.462	0.460
Palmolein	0.492	0.502
Linseed	0.449	0.455
Eucalyptus	0.429	0.432
Pig	0.474	0.469
Mustard	0.230	0.229
Neem	0.299	0.285
Castor	0.297	0.305

a differential Gaussmeter with a Hall probe to an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$. Solid specimens were powdered thoroughly to eliminate any orientation effects and uniform filling of the tubes was ensured to avoid errors due to packing. The tubes were filled to the same level. The data obtained by the Gouy method were checked by measuring the magnetic susceptibility by the Quincke method. The values obtained by these two methods agreed very well (Table 2). In the Quincke method, with oils of high viscosity and low surface tension, reproducible results were obtained only if sufficient time was allowed for the oil to rise in the magnetic field. For instance, in the case of castor oil, a steady level was obtained only after 20 min of immersion in the magnetic field.

Repeated measurements of susceptibility for each sample showed a variation of only $\pm 2\%$.

Results and Discussion

The volume susceptibilities of eleven oils measured at room temperature are given in Table 3. A comparison of these values indicates that oils fall into two groups. One group has lower density and viscosity, but higher surface tension and diamagnetic susceptibility. The second group has relatively higher density and viscosity, but lower surface tension and diamagnetic susceptibility.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF FIELD STRENGTH ON SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF OILS

Oils	-10 ⁻⁶ (Volume susceptibility) at field strength of		
	8 kG	10 kG	12 kG
Coconut	0.499	0.477	0.413
Refined	0.469	0.459	0.399
Gingelly	0.529	0.499	0.417
Groundnut	0.534	0.462	0.423
Palmolein	0.522	0.492	0.427
Linseed	0.488	0.499	0.391
Eucalyptus	0.466	0.429	0.378
Pig	0.490	0.474	0.400
Mustard	0.300	0.230	0.211
Neem	0.320	0.299	0.245
Castor	0.328	0.277	0.262

An interesting observation was made when the magnetic field was varied from 8 to 12 kG. The susceptibility of each sample decreased slightly with increasing field (Table 3). This may be due to the presence of extremely minute amounts of some paramagnetic metal ions in the oils. Under low fields, the paramagnetic behaviour might be so insignificant that it is masked by the diamagnetic character of the oil. However, under high fields the paramagnetic contribution might become significant and thus affect the measured diamagnetic susceptibility. It appears that paramagnetic impurity has insignificant temperature effect as indicated by the constancy of the values at different temperatures. Another possibility for the field effect would involve creation of paramagnetic centres in the constituents of the oils. But the probability of such an effect is likely to be very low.

A curious observation was made when the susceptibility of groundnut and gingelly oilcake was measured (Table 4). The cakes show paramagnetic behaviour unlike the corresponding oils and seeds. What causes paramagnetic behaviour in cakes is obscure. A possibility is contamination by metals, especially iron, during extraction of oil in a steel mill. However, this is ruled out since cakes from wooden mill also exhibited the same paramagnetism. All oilseeds have iron content, but in varying amounts. Iron is likely to be retained in the cake which would account for the paramagnetic behaviour of the cakes. This argument is supported by the higher susceptibility of gingelly cake compared to

that of groundnut cake because gingelly seeds have about 10 mg iron per 100 g compared to that in groundnut seeds, 2 mg per 100 g^{1,6} (Table 1).

TABLE 4—VOLUME SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF OIL CAKES AND OIL SEEDS

Material	10 ⁻⁶ (Volume susceptibility at 10 kG)			
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Groundnut cake	1.358	1.145	2.255	2.212
Gingelly cake	8.05	7.643	6.821	5.481
Groundnut seed			-0.109*	
Gingelly seed			-0.080*	

*Mean of ten trials.

Another possible explanation for the paramagnetic behaviour of an oilcake may lie in assuming the formation of paramagnetic centres during crushing. The nature of such changes occurring during crushing is not clear. A paramagnetic metal ion present in the seed may be complexed by the fibrous proteins such that the paramagnetic character of the ion is quenched. In the cake, this situation might change involving the destruction of the complex leading to the 'liberation' of the metal ion. Filing and breaking of the horn were shown to produce, by esr studies, free radicals due to molecular chain breaking which is analogous to the present observation⁷.

The magnitude of the volume susceptibility of a particular cake appears to be influenced by the amount of residual oil in it. The more 'dry' is the cake containing less oil, more is the susceptibility.

Samples of a cake obtained from various sources did not have the same value of magnetic susceptibility. This might be due to different degrees of crushing in various mills. Rice and its flour showed diamagnetic susceptibility of the same magnitude. A similar observation was made with wheat and its flour. This rules out any metal contamination during crushing in the mill. Hence, the paramagnetic behaviour of oil cakes may be due to some structural transformations in the constituents of the seeds during the crushing process. Further work is in progress with a view to understanding this phenomenon.

References

1. Y. G. DEOSTAHLE, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 988.
2. K. A. WILLIAMS, "Oils Fats and Fatty Acids", 4th. ed., J. A. Churchill Ltd., 1960.
3. H. G. KRISCHENBAUER, "Fats and Oils—An Outline of Their Chemistry and Technology", 2nd. ed., Reinhold, New York, 1960.
4. L. V. COCKS and C. VAN REDE, "Laboratory Handbook for Oils and Fats Analysis", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
5. L. F. BATES, "Modern Magnetism", 4th. ed., Cambridge University Press, 1963, p. 115.
6. *The Wealth of India*, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1972, Vol. 9, p. 286.
7. H. M. ASSENHEIM, "Introduction to ESR", Hilger Watts Ltd., London, 1966, p. 155.

Synthesis of Some Thiazole Substituted Phenylimino-4-thiazolidinones

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones^{1,2} and in view of their pharmacological activities³, the syntheses of the title compounds have been made in our present study.

In the present investigation unsymmetrical thiocarbamides (2) were synthesised by condensing 2-substituted amino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazoles (1)⁴ with arylisothiocyanates. The thiocarbamides were condensed with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid to furnish the thiazolidinones. There was possibility of formation of two products, 3a and 3b. Tlc study indicated the presence of only one product. The authenticity of the compound was further confirmed by the chemical method. When the product, obtained by the condensation of *N*²-*p*-(2'-anilinothiazol-4'-yl)phenyl-*N*²-phenylthiocarbamide and chloroacetic acid, was hydrolysed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the filtrate after separation of thiazolidione (m.p. 200°), on basification gave 2-anilino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazole (m.p. 139°). The m.p.s., agreed with the reported values^{4,5}. Similarly, the structures of other thiazolidinones were chemically confirmed. There is formation of thiazolidione and aminophenylthiazoles in each case. This supports the structure 3a for the 4-thiazolidinones.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The pmr spectra were studied in CDCl₃ on a Varian T-60 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard.

*Synthesis of N*²-[*p*-(2-anilinothiazol-4'-yl)phenyl]-*N*²-phenylthiocarbamide 2 (as representative case): A solution of 2-anilino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazole (0.01 mol, 2.67 g) and phenylisothiocyanate (0.012 mol, 1.62 g) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 h. After cooling, the crystalline thiocarbamide was filtered and dried. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 220°. Similarly, other thiocarbamides were prepared and their characterisations are recorded in Table 1; ν_{max} 1215-1250 (C=S stretching), 3150-3300 (NH stretching), 1560-1580 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) and characteristic absorptions of thiazole ring.

Synthesis of 2-p-(2'-phenyl aminothiazol-4'-yl)-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone 3a (as representative case): A mixture of *N*²-*p*-(2-anilino-